

AUTOMATION OF ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE TESTING

Dean Dringenburg and Robert Siefker
Naval Avionics Center
6000 East 21st Street
Indianapolis, Indiana 46218

ABSTRACT

Automation of EMI testing is becoming common at many EMI test facilities. Commercial automated systems have even become available of the past few years. The Naval Avionics Center has developed its own EMI automation to enhance and aid in testing. This automation uses a Hewlett Packard HP1000A Mainframe computer and a Hewlett Packard 8566A Spectrum Analyzer.

This paper details the program structure and some of the methods required to complete such a program on the equipment chosen. Included is a description of the Broadband-Narrowband determination technique of checking for a 3 dB amplitude change for a 10 dB change in receiver bandwidth.

INTRODUCTION

The Naval Avionics Center (NAC) is a field activity of the Naval Air Systems Command and as such plays a key role in the development of aviation electronics (avionics) systems for use by Fleet aircraft. Included in the NAC charter is the authority to design hardware for Fleet use, specify and procure hardware from a variety of sources including commercial suppliers and other Government agencies, and to act as the data validation activity when second sources for critical weapon systems are required. In all three roles, the complete analysis of complex avionics systems is frequently required. Included in these analyses is the evaluation of the EMI/EMC characteristics of the systems. Approximately 75 EMI Tests are performed at NAC each year ranging in complexity from simple development testing of a breadboard power supply, to a complete MIL-STD-461 test regimen. In addition to simply establishing compliance with a specification, the NAC EMI Staff is required to analyze the performance of each system and to accurately predict its suitability for Fleet use. Thus, the flexibility to examine emissions in great detail is required in the EMI Test Laboratory.

The sheer volume of data taken during EMI testing makes it a prime candidate for automation. During emissions testing for example, the test regimen (simplified) consists of eight distinct steps:

- assembly of the test setup,
- initialization of the setup (i.e., calibration, etc.),
- measurement of the ambient emission level,
- measurement of the emissions from the unit under test,
- correction of the data for probe/antenna factor, cable loss, etc.,
- determining broadband/narrowband signal classification where applicable,
- representing the data in plots and tables suitable for reports, and
- reporting the results.

A glance at this list reveals the labor intensive nature of emission testing. When all emissions data are processed manually, approximately 80 percent of

the effort is labor related directly to measuring, reducing or presenting data. Any effort so labor intensive is clearly ripe for automation.

An orderly engineering approach to the task of automating emissions measurements requires a logical progression through five steps. These are:

1. Select the basic hardware approach.
2. Define the automated system requirements.
3. Define the software system requirements.
4. Plan the software flow.
5. Write the required software in modular form.

HARDWARE APPROACH

The EMI testing performed by NAC frequently goes far beyond simply certifying compliance with the specification. Often, the emissions of avionics systems are carefully examined to determine the exact nature of the emissions. This permits the subsequent evaluation of the EMC impact of the system on the host aircraft. For this reason, the flexibility of the spectrum analyzer has offered great appeal to the EMI Engineers and has been in use as the basic measurement instrument at NAC for many years. Until 1982, the instrument used by the NAC EMI Lab was the HP-8555A installed in an HP-141 mainframe. In 1981, the decision was made to replace the aging HP-8555A with the more modern HP-8566A Spectrum Analyzer. The advantages of this unit over its older cousin are many, but perhaps the most significant is its ability to operate as part of the IEEE-488 instrument bus.

At approximately the same time, the concept of automating equipment evaluation testing was being carefully examined by several of the other elements at NAC. A coordinated selection process resulted in the selection of the HP-1000A Computer as the standard metrology computer at NAC. Several computers were purchased, one of which was dedicated to EMI testing. In addition, the HP-2647 and HP-2648 Graphics Terminals were selected as the principle operator interface. Figure 1 is a diagram of the NAC EMI test hardware.

SYSTEM AND SOFTWARE PERFORMANCE

The system functional requirements directly track those previously listed for EMI testing. Namely, initialization, ambient measurement, EMI data measurement, data correction, broadband/narrowband (BB/NB) determination, data presentation, and report preparation. In each of these areas, the computer is able to assist in streamlining the process.

It should be noted that the selection of a predominantly Hewlett Packard based system was based on the evaluation of many factors including GSA contractual arrangements, IEEE 488 bus compatibility, commonality with other metrology efforts, etc. This selection is not intended to endorse HP and it is worth noting that there are many excellent sources of similar EMI metrology equipment.

Figure 1

During initialization, the computer will first lead the operator through a series of prompting messages to establish the identity of the unit under test (UUT) and the operator, and whether a new test or the continuation of a previous test. If a new test is indicated, the operator enters whether it is a "standard test"; i.e., one where standard limits are to be imposed, or special test where nonstandard limits are to be entered by the operator, and the details of the test configuration. (Standard test configurations are stored in memory.) During the initialization, the computer compares the identification numbers of the instruments with those listed in memory. These data, when entered, become part of the memory and will not need re-entry in the future. The operator is prompted through a series of questions about the UUT such as number of leads to be tested during conducted emissions, the frequency range of any receivers or transmitters, and other data needed to properly identify "standard" test limits.

Once all of the initialization data is entered, the EMI operator is prompted through the various Emission Tests. The operator has complete control over the order in which tests are performed; i.e., CE01 may be performed first or last as is desired. Within the test method, the computer will gather data over the frequency range of the probe/antenna and prompt the operator to change either the probe/antenna, the mode or the lead being tested. In this manner, the operator is "led" through the test. At any time, the operator can assume "local" control of the spectrum analyzer to examine any signals of interest. For those tests requiring broadband/narrowband determination, the computer causes a second spectrum analyzer scan to be made at a different bandwidth from the first. The data are examined for change of amplitude and BB/NB categorization is made. (This process is described in detail in a later section.) Once the BB/NB determination is made, the operator is shown the plot of data as categorized and the operator then may edit the data and move signals from one category to the

other. Once satisfied with the validity of the data, the operator can direct the computer to store the data on the system disk, or to plot the data on a printer, or both.

The system permits nearly total flexibility in both frequency and amplitude limits; however, the standard limits of MIL-STD-461B Parts 2, 5, and 6 and MIL-STD-461A with or without Notices 3 or 6, are stored in memory and may be selected by the operator.

SOFTWARE APPROACH

A modular or structured software system was chosen. This decision was prompted by more than just good engineering practice. It was made necessary by an idiosyncrasy of the HP-1000A. The total memory capacity of the HP-1000A is 512K bytes and should be adequate for almost any programming, structured or not. However, the memory is segmented into 32K portions for each of what is assumed to be many users. (Recently, Hewlett Packard has introduced an option called VC+ to circumvent this characteristic, but when the majority of this software was written, the limitation on total memory that could be used "on line" was 32K.) This made the modular programming approach the only one possible.

The program was constructed in five basic sections - initialization, test setup, collection and correction of data, detailed data lists and graphs, and overall semilog graphing. The diagram in Figure 2 shows the overall program. Each section is itself modularized for simplification and because of the memory limitation previously discussed.

Figure 2

Briefly, the function and objective of each major module is as follows:

Test Initialization

1. Enter required test
2. Permit change of frequency range and test limits
3. Set desired base parameters
4. Enter leads and modes
5. Calibration check
6. Store modified setup

Test Setup

1. Prompt operator with proper lead, mode, setup parameters
2. Set proper span for analyzer
3. Write specification to analyzer
4. Permit change of equipment list
5. Collect data

Data Collection

1. Read data
2. Correct data
3. Reduce data and store in memory

Data List and Graph (if desired)

1. Print graph from analyzer screen
2. Print table of discrete data points (frequency and amplitude) designated by operator

Semilog Graph

1. Determine BB/NB classification
2. Permit editing BB/NB files
3. Print semilog graph of corrected BB/NB data

Looking at each module in turn:

The first program segment called is the initialization routine. These nine modules establish the basic parameters of the test and store data about the test sample and the test setup.

"Initial 1" establishes the basic test parameters. The military standard and applicable notices are entered in response to user prompts. The operator selects the tests to be performed; e.g., CE01, RE02, etc., and enters a unique, locally assigned project number. This project number is subsequently used to identify data storage files and other storage files related to the test project.

"Initial 2" requires no operator interaction. It establishes standard conditions based on the tests and standards selected previously. Included is the establishment of spectrum analyzer start/stop frequencies and other pertinent parameters for the entire test span.

"Initial 3" continues the establishment of parameters for the test by retrieving the file of previously stored data. These data are stored under the file name HXXXYY, where H is a constant denoting a "heading" file, XXX is the unique project number and YY is a digraph representing the particular test being performed; e.g., C1 for CE01, R2 for RE02, etc. From this file, the frequency range established in "Initial 2" will be modified to match previously stored special test conditions. If this is the first time for a test to be performed, the user is led through a series of prompts and may modify test parameters as appropriate. Any modification recalled will be stored under the heading file and will be automatically entered during future tests unless further modified.

"Initial 4" allows the operator to enter the test at any time. In essence, it is an interrupt routine. The operator may wish to exercise this option to repeat a segment of data or to limit the test without

modifying the heading file. The operator is informed as to the status of the test; i.e., graph number and frequency, at the time of interrupt. The test will automatically resume from the last frequency taken or a different frequency may be designated.

"Initial 5" allows for the entry of test sample information such as number of leads to be tested during CE01 and CE03, operating modes, and antenna positions to be used during RE01 and RE02. If the test is a continuation of previous tests, the previously entered information is displayed and may be modified, if needed. If the test is a new test, the operator is prompted through a series of inputs required to gather the information which is then stored in the heading file for reference.

"Initial 6" requires no operator input and calculates the number of tests and further test parameters based on test sample data.

"Initial 7" prompts the operator to calibrate the equipment requiring calibration. In addition, a user prompt is displayed to remind the operator to check serial numbers with those in the heading file. (The serial number of certain equipment can be critical since the correction factors may vary from one unit to another.)

"Initial 8" retrieves the limits from memory applicable to the standard selected. The operator may enter a different limit by entering the end and "break" points of the limit on the semilog graph. The limits are then added to the heading file. If this is the continuation of previous testing, the previously stored limits will be recalled from the heading file.

"Initial 9" is used to recall the first frequency span to be tested. This is used to create prompts to the operator as to which current probe/antenna should be connected first.

The next major segment of the software is a group of modules which collect and store the emissions data. There are six modules in the "Test" section and three in the "Data" section.

"Test 1" establishes the test equipment file. Antenna factors, cable and attenuator losses, probe factors, etc., are recalled for the "standard" test configuration.

"Test 2" permits the operator to edit the test configuration in any way desired. The "standard" equipment list with associated performance parameters is displayed for operator review. Any item may be changed by simply typing over the displayed data. Changes are normally required when a particular equipment or cable is in use in another test setup in the EMI Lab.

"Test 3" requires no operator input and is used to set the spectrum analyzer controls over the IEEE-488 bus. At this time, an actual measurement of emissions occurs but the measured data are not yet stored in memory. The operator sees the spectrum analyzer output, uncorrected and in real time, in preparation for the "official" or "record" data scan that will occur in "Test 6". Also included in this module is the calculation of an array of twenty equally spaced points which define the test limits. These limits are used by the operator to check the emissions for out-of-tolerance conditions.

"Test 4" is a correction routine which adjusts the array calculated in Test 3 for the losses/gains

in the test system. This allows the limit line to be presented to the operator on the spectrum analyzer screen in real time for direct data comparison. Note that the limit line on this linear plot appears different from in the final semilogarithmic output in that the limit is corrected, often resulting in a rather "strange" looking limit line. In the final output, the data are corrected and the limit line appears "normal" (as published in the military standards).

"Test 5" is a short routine which actually draws the adjusted limit line calculated in "Test 4" on the spectrum analyzer screen.

"Test 6" is the final module in the test segment. It is in this module that the "official" or final data are gathered and stored. The analyzer screen displays the parameters of the measurement and the operator still has the option to change these parameters. If he exercises that option, the program returns to Test 2 and any changes are made. If the operator is satisfied in all respects, a user prompt asks if a hard copy and/or tabular list is desired. If one or both is desired, a flag is set and the selected option will be produced later. In any case, the operator causes the "official" measurement to begin by answering that user prompt. During the measurement phase, the spectrum analyzer is placed in continuous sweep, peak hold mode. This means that the peak amplitude measured in any of the 1001 data "cells" of the screen during what is an indefinite number of sweeps, will be retained as the final amplitude of that cell. When the operator is satisfied that a sufficient number of sweeps have been gathered, the return key on the terminal is depressed (in response to a terminal screen prompt) and the analyzer is changed to the single sweep mode. One final scan is made in single sweep after which the analyzer waits to transfer its memory to the IEEE-488 bus. At this point, the "official" or "record" data collection is completed. The program automatically proceeds to the next segment of the program where data correction reduction and storage is accomplished.

At the conclusion of data reduction and storage, if the operator has selected the option of receiving hard copy, the program also proceeds to the "detail" segment of the program where these data copies are produced. Once these segments have completed their operation, the program returns to Test 1 for the next frequency span.

This looping continues until the final span is completed after which the program branches to the "graph" segment of the program. The functions of these segments will be described in greater detail in later sections of this paper. (It should be noted that the option to produce hard copies is seldom exercised during EMI Tests since the reduced data from each frequency span will ultimately be plotted in an aggregate semilogarithmic plot of all of the data gathered.)

In order to enable understanding of the functions of the data and storage segment, it is first necessary to digress slightly and describe the basic algorithm associated with data reduction and BB/NB classification.

Initially, the intent was to save (on a floppy disk) all data collected as well as all pertinent parametric data. The magnitude of the undertaking soon overwhelmed the resources of the HP 1000 based system since as many as 24,000 data points might be taken during a single test. It was concluded that

the integrity of the EMI data set would be virtually unaffected by examining a selected sample of data. The number of final data points was selected to be 574 since this was the limit that could be accepted by the graphics terminal. Thus established, the method of data reduction was simply to retain the maximum amplitude signal in each of 574 "cells" as the amplitude of the cell.

The method of broadband/narrowband classification involved consideration of two basic algorithms.

1. Make two successive scans with the spectrum analyzer with different predetection ("rf") bandwidths, compare the two scans, and look for a change in amplitude of each individual cell.

2. Make one scan with the spectrum analyzer and examine the amplitude of contiguous cells for a specified rate of change.

Both algorithms 1 and 2 were the subject of analytical and empirical review. The two methods were found equally likely to properly classify signals but Method 1 was judged to be less difficult to implement. Hence, Method 1 was selected.

The final algorithm selected was to change the spectrum analyzer bandwidth by a factor of 10, and examine each data cell for a corresponding change in amplitude of more than 3 dB. The basic concept being that a narrowband signal will change by some amount between 3 and 10 dB depending on the specific spectrum of the signal. Any signal changing by less than 3 dB is removed from the BB file. In other words, the BB file is established by default by eliminating the NB signals. The "gap" left by deleting the NB signal is "filled" by averaging the signal levels in the adjacent cells and assigning this average value to the cells formerly containing the NB signal, thus retaining a "smooth" appearance to the BB plot. Once the BB/NB determination is made, the BB data are corrected to reflect the 1 MHz bandwidth nature of the military standard limit. This "corrected" BB file is retained for final reporting.

A strong NB signal couples energy to the passband "skirts" of a scanning spectrum analyzer. (In essence, the IF filter bandpass is traced.) This results in the base of a narrowband signal appearing wider than it actually is; i.e., "blooming" and would result in a distorted view of things if only the cell at the center frequency of the strong narrowband signal was excised while the "bloomed" base remained. A special algorithm was created to counteract the "blooming" base of a strong narrowband signal as viewed on a spectrum analyzer. The amplitude of a narrowband signal viewed on the HP-8566A falls off at a rate of approximately 10 dB per receiver bandwidth from the center frequency. Therefore, the frequency span of such a signal can be described by the following formula:

$$F = F_o + (A - (L - 10)) * BW / 10$$

where F is the frequency span of the NB signal to be deleted
F_o is the center frequency of the NB signal
A is the maximum amplitude of the NB signal
L is the applicable limit
BW is the receiver bandwidth

The term L - 10 is used to ensure that the excised signal will fall below the BB limit line by 10 dB. The interpolation, or averaging, of the BB data then is used to smooth the "hole" left by removing this relatively wide span. The validity of this interpo-

lation is established by the empirical observation that BB signal amplitudes do not typically change rapidly versus frequency and that any BB signals present would be masked by the "bloomed" NB signal anyway. The conclusion then is reached that no significant additional errors are introduced by this method and certainly the plot is much easier to interpret than if it had several "holes" in it.

The NB plot is simply a graph of the emissions data taken with the narrower of the two bandwidths. The last step in the automated plot routine is to add the corrected ambient measurement data to the plots of BB and NB data.

Having now described the technique used for data collection and processing, let us return to a description of the software used to collect and store data.

The data collected for each individual frequency span must be reduced and stored in a file. These functions are performed by the three "Data" modules. These modules collect, correct, reduce and store the data.

"Data 1" interacts with the spectrum analyzer, checking to see that the last sweep is complete, and once this condition is satisfied, reads the 1001 data "cells" from the analyzer, storing them in an array.

"Data 2" applies correction including probe/antenna factor, preamplifier gain, cable losses and bandwidth factors as appropriate. The original uncorrected data are retained in memory and a new corrected array is stored.

"Data 3" reduces the data as described earlier. The reduced data set is then stored in a data file with a name derived from the heading file associated with the test; i.e., DXXXXY where the XXXXY string is the same as assigned during the heading file name and the D denotes a data file. This data file is stored as a direct access file with amplitude only stored in each of the 574 data cells. The frequency of each cell is derived from the algorithm based on the start and stop frequency of the test and need not be stored. This permits a major reduction in file space requirements.

Once the data are gathered and reduced, only reduced data are stored in permanent files. In order to allow a retention of the unreduced data, either "raw" or corrected, the operator is given the option of making a linear plot of the spectrum analyzer screen during the test. This option is most frequently exercised during developmental testing or EMC analysis where a limited frequency range is involved, or when extremely fine grained data are desired. There is almost no limit to the resolution available during this type of test since the total frequency span of the spectrum analyzer can be set arbitrarily small and the plot still contains 1001 data points. The use of this option during EMI qualification testing is infrequent and is essentially limited to use during BB/NB editing to make fine grained analyses of potentially misclassified signals. The linear plots are generated by six "Detail" modules.

"Detail 1" creates a heading line for the plot containing the name of the operator, project name, date, and three lines of free text for operator comments.

"Detail 2" gives the operator the option to designate a specific set of previously collected data

for tabular listing. The operator designates the desired data points with the spectrum analyzer marker one at a time. Each time a point is selected, the raw and uncorrected data are called from memory and stored in a new three dimensional matrix containing frequency, raw, and corrected data.

"Details 3, 4, and 5" actually transfer the graphics onto the graphics terminal screen. "Detail 3" creates the linear grid on the screen. "Detail 4" transfers the spectrum analyzer labels to the terminal screen. "Detail 5" "draws" the uncorrected data and the corrected limit line on the terminal screen. The operator may decide at this point to merely examine the data on the large screen of the graphics terminal or may elect to produce a "hard copy" on the printer.

"Detail 6" causes the terminal screen to be dumped to the printer and follows this dump by a tabular listing of the three dimensional matrix stored during "Detail 2." The use of a graphics terminal made this segment fairly simple to write in that the ability to dump the screen to a printer is a standard function of the terminal.

The last major software segment produces report ready semilogarithmic graphs from the reduced data files. This segment is divided into six modules titled "Graph 1" through "Graph 6".

"Graph 1" performs the BB/NB classification as described earlier.

"Graphs 2 through 5" produce the semilog graph on the terminal screen.

"Graph 2" produces the semilog grid including frequency and amplitude labels.

"Graph 3" prints the remaining labels including date, unit under test, operator, test and operator comments.

"Graph 4" produces the limit line on the terminal screen.

"Graph 5" permits operator interaction and allows editing of the BB and NB plots. If editing is desired, the frequency of any signal to be edited is entered and the signal is deleted from the appropriate file. In addition, the operator may change the vertical scale (ordinate) on the graph.

"Graph 6" dumps the screen to the plotter/printer and is functionally very similar to "Detail 6". Figures 3 through 8 show a set of sample plots. Figures 3 and 4 show logarithmic plots of CE03 NB and BB data respectively over the frequency range of 15 kHz to 50 GHz. These are typical of the plots associated with final reports of EMI qualification testing. Figure 5 is a linear plot of uncorrected spectrum analyzer data representing the same CE03 emissions over the frequency range 0 MHz to 10 MHz. Note the adjusted limit line superimposed on the unadjusted data. This plot is typical of that which would be made during failure mechanism analysis, or operator investigation of apparent anomalies. [While it happens that 0 Hz to 10 MHz is a standard frequency span covered during CE03 testing, this plot could have been made over any arbitrarily selected span, in whatever detail (i.e., video bandwidth, scan speed, predetection bandwidth, frequency span, etc.) desired.] Figure 6 is the tabular listing generated from the data taken concurrent with the generation of Figure 5.

Figures 3 and 4

TEST: CE03 MIL-STD-461B Part 2
B/441 PROJECT NUMBER: 999

DATE: 7 FEB 1985

TITLE: CE03 TEST

MEASUREMENT TYPE: NARROWBAND
UUT MODE: TEST MODE 1
LEAD: TEST LEAD 1

TEST TECHNICIAN: DEAN DRINGENBURG
TEST SAMPLE: UNIT UNDER TEST

GRAPH STEP 2

CORRECTED LOG REF: +80 dBuA

MEASUREMENT # 12

Figure 5

TEST: CE03 MIL-STD-461B Part 2
B/441 PROJECT NUMBER: 999

DATE: 7 FEB 1985

TITLE: CE03 TEST

MEASUREMENT TYPE: NARROWBAND
UUT MODE: TEST MODE 1
LEAD: TEST LEAD 1

TEST TECHNICIAN: DEAN DRINGENBURG
TEST SAMPLE: UNIT UNDER TEST

GRAPH STEP 2

CORRECTED LOG REF: +80 dBuA

MEASUREMENT # 12

Equipment Description	Test Equipment Tab e	IIJ Number
HP8566 Spectrum Analyzer		31892/31893
IF Bandwidth 10 kHz		
STOD 91550-1 Probe		
Cable/Filter Loss (dB)	1	
External Attenuator (dB)	0	
Preamp Gain (dB)	0	

PARTIAL DATA TABLE

Frequency	Uncorrected Level	Corrected Level
1. 1.01 MHz	38.70 dBuV	25.05 dBuA
2. 6.02 MHz	29.35 dBuV	15.05 dBuA
3. 7.03 MHz	23.88 dBuV	9.58 dBuA
4. 8.03 MHz	20.00 dBuV	5.70 dBuA
5. 9.03 MHz	20.00 dBuV	5.70 dBuA
6. 9.87 MHz	20.00 dBuV	5.70 dBuA

Figure 6

Figures 7 and 8 show typical RE02 BB and NB plots respectively over the full range of the standard test.

Figures 7 and 8

CONCLUSIONS

The automated system described in this paper has been in place and operational for the past year at the Naval Avionics Center. Certain segments of the system have been in use for over two years. The efficacy of the system was, if anything, initially underestimated. The backlog of EMI Tests has been reduced substantially and the emissions tests that once consumed several weeks can now be completed in a few days. The improved efficiency of the testing has had several desirable side effects as well. First, the EMC Engineer once had to struggle with tedious computations to convert dBm (from the spectrum analyzer screen) into the proper dimensions. Errors were not uncommon and by the time all of the adjustments were made the EMC Engineer frequently found that many minutes had passed. The automated system permits the EMC Engineer to examine and analyze corrected data in real time and without the potential for errors in calculation.

The second side effect is closely related to the first. The rapid reduction of data and greatly reduced test time have resulted in the improved affordability of developmental EMI testing. This has made such developmental EMI testing much more appealing to the general engineering community. The ability of the EMI Lab personnel to provide meaningful emissions data on a breadboard or advanced development model in a few hours or a day, with a total cost of a few hundred dollars, has been instrumental in bringing this valuable engineering design tool within the range of economic desirability for many project engineers.

The production of report-ready graphs is the key to the economy of the effort. The automated determination of BB/NB is in turn key to the production of report ready graphs. Even when the

automation effort at NAC had progressed to the point that all data were being taken automatically and corrections applied by the computer, the EMI operator still had to spend hours comparing data graphs to determine BB/NB categorizations and then had to manually generate new plots of the categorized signals. The accuracy of the BB/NB determination algorithm has proven to be over 99 percent. The occasional incorrectly categorized signals tend to be either weak narrowband signals that just "peek" out of the broadband background or are doublets or triplets of narrowband signals with spacings making them appear broadband to the algorithm. The ability to electronically edit the respective data files eliminates the occasional erroneously categorized signal and permits the true time and cost saving of emissions automation to be realized.

The accurate gathering of EMI data has traditionally required highly competent operators. While the automated measurement and graphing of data are great time savers, a number of very critical operations must still be performed by a highly trained, competent operator. During the preceding description of system operation, many operator options were described. The EMI operator must make intelligent decisions at many of these points by analyzing the technical situation and choosing the correct option. For example, in the description of "Test 6", the statement "If the operator is satisfied in all respects, ..." is made without explaining what it means to be "satisfied". To be satisfied, the operator must call on his experience to determine that no amplifiers, spectrum analyzers or other "linear" elements are overdriven, no out-of-band interfering signals are causing spurious responses in the spectrum analyzer, or any other condition exists to cause erroneous data. A second example, also related to "Test 6", describes the number of sweeps taken by the spectrum analyzer as "indefinite". While the number of sweeps is indeed indefinite, it is certainly not arbitrary. The judgement of the EMI operator is critical in making the judgement as to when enough sweeps have been completed. The point is, the required skill of the operator is not reduced by this method of automation.